

June 30, 2024

<https://ijoabs.com/>
[DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.)

Developing Culture of Periodic Markets to Create Sustainable Livelihoods for Ethnic Minorities in Northern Vietnam

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Received Date: 20-Mar-2024

Accepted Date: 27-April-2024

Published Date: 30-June-2024

Abstract:

The goal of the article is to learn about the unique Indigenous cultural values of ethnic minorities' s Periodic markets in northern Vietnam. The article assesses the current Periodic market operations of ethnic minorities from north Vietnam today. From there, analyses and recommendations are made to preserve the Indigenous cultural values of the Periodic market and its role in creating sustainable livelihoods for ethnic minorities in the northern mountainous region of Vietnam.

Keywords: *Periodic markets, sustainable livelihoods, ethnic minorities, northern Vietnam*

1. Introduction

In today's society, along with the rapid development of a series of advanced technologies, traditional markets are becoming more and more inferior to convenience stores or modern supermarkets. However, in many cultures around the world such as Korea and Thailand, the simple beauty of the traditional market has persisted strongly over time, attracting thousands of tourists every year. It can be said that it is the unique cultural values and the beauty of the local people that have successfully created the unmistakable beauty of each market in each region.

No exception, the fair market in the northern mountains of our country still exists as a traditional cultural beauty. Coming to the session market, visitors can experience a cultural space full of community. It is a place where ethnic minorities live and live together, where local customs and practices are displayed and cherished to the fullest. In particular, traditional markets in the highlands are organized simply, when you just need to spread a tarpaulin, a raincoat and then sell homemade handicrafts, meatballs, a few bananas, or bunches of vegetables grown in the garden...

Moreover, as studied in many previous publications, the role of fairs is important in enhancing regional economic activity, as it promotes the development and growth of a region (McGrath et al., 1993). These rural bazaars are responsible for connecting the marketing system with the surrounding villages, thereby paving the way for the establishment of a local trade network across emerging economies (Dokmeci et al., 2006).

This motivates us to study the cultural value of the Northern mountainous fair market and the far-reaching influence of the object on the sustainable livelihood of local people. That is, what specific effects has the

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commercial attraction along with the diverse forms of tourism of the fair market had on the social security of local people?

The structure of the article in addition to the introduction includes: Research overview, Typical situation of some markets in the North, The influence of market culture on sustainable livelihoods and Conclusion.

2. Literature review

2.1. Cultural values of Periodic markets

As Aram (2019) periodic markets are a type of market allowing people to trade rural goods with products from cities. Whether urban areas or rural settlements, this type of market is the first form of exchanging space to occur (Dokmeci, 2005) thus it has a long antiquity (Aram, 2019). Unlike daily markets, periodic markets are organized at a definite location with predetermined time intervals. (Velayudhan, 2014) Individuals participate in the market directly interacting with one another to achieve their different goals, ranging from economic gains to social and cultural interactions. (Aram, 2019) The most crucial trade space in rural areas in Africa, Asia, and Latin America, these markets not only satisfy shopping demand but also help farmers gain income from selling agricultural produce and manufactured items. (Zhengying Liu et al., 2022) Quality and price of the selling goods varies depending on the market's proximity to urban residential areas and the income of the neighborhoods near the markets. (Dokmeci 2005, according to Skinner (1964)

Many traditional cultural heritages of Vietnamese ethnic groups have been recognized as world cultural heritage, national cultural heritage, typically such as: worship of Hung King, ancestor worship, Central Highlands gong cultural space, Phu Tho xoan singing, etc. Every year, Vietnam has about 8,000 festivals, of which many folk festivals are community-based, which is a valuable material for the development of cultural tourism.

Historical and cultural tourism is associated with admiring and exploring cultural spaces such as gong cultural space, in Dak Lak - intangible cultural heritage, Thai xòe art heritage (Thai people in the Northwest region)... Festival tourism is associated with traditional festivals of ethnic minorities, as well as experiencing intangible culture, admiring and enjoying traditional dishes, folk songs, typical dances of ethnic minorities, such as the Gau Cao festival (Ha Giang, Lao Cai), Mo Muong (Hoa Binh), trumpet art of the Mong people (Moc Chau district, Son La), Kate festival of Cham people (Ninh Thuan), Hue court music...

Tourism to experience the life of ethnic minorities helps visitors have new discoveries, directly immerse themselves in local life, do daily tasks with local people and cook meals imbued with regional identity. In particular, the fair market is a unique cultural feature of Vietnam's ethnic minorities. Exploiting the fair market in cultural tourism products brings tourism a multi-dimensional reference corner. Coming to the session market, visitors are like witnesses to the trading process and are also the ones who take the initiative in trading transactions here. Coming to the fair market is also a way to experience emotional exchanges in the social life of ethnic minority people. Ethnic minority people go to the fair not only to shop for essential items, but also a place for cultural exchange of ethnic minorities, a place to converge traditional cultural activities of ethnic minorities such as passing on songs, dancing, inviting each other to have a cup of wine...

The fair market stores a treasure trove of culinary culture, costumes, music... extremely interesting of the local people. People come to the market of all ages from old to young, especially young men and women. Mothers and women buy and sell agricultural products, buy and repair dresses. Husbands meet friends, blow trumpets, drink cups of fragrant corn wine. Children follow their parents to the market to eat hot bowls of pho, buy a few more donuts to take home, while men and women go on dates and exchanges, creating a lively and joyful scene. Coming to the session market, the food and beverage shops are always crowded with diners. The pungent aroma of rustic dishes is smoky to dispel the cold wind and dew. Both locals and tourists cannot resist the attraction of specialties with bold mountain and forest flavor. In addition, coming to the fair, visitors will have access to unique traditional handicrafts of ethnic minorities, shopping for traditional handicrafts such as brocade, paper, incense, indigo, blacksmithing and knitting products... According to many tourism experts, the differences in landscape, national culture, and typical products make the fair market a great attraction for tourists from all over

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the world. If the fair is well organized, associated with cultural activities, the festival not only contributes to creating output for local products but can completely form new tourism products.

Cultural tourism products of ethnic minorities.

Cultural tourism products are a package of services and goods built on the basis of cultural resources and tourist needs. In areas with rich and unique folk cultural heritage tourism resources, there are many values, which will create attractive tourism products. The characteristics of abundant resources and high specificity have created favorable conditions for diverse and attractive cultural products that have a high ability to attract tourists. Tourist establishments are both a place of production and a place of service provision, so tourists who want to consume must go to tourist establishments, tourist spots and resorts to enjoy. Therefore, due to this characteristic, strong promotion is required to attract tourists.

On the other hand, tourism products are strictly seasonal. It is not possible to watch festivals and markets on weekdays. It is impossible to buy specialties in the off-season... Seasonality also leads to the "overload" of tourism (festivals, events, etc.). This feature also requires cultural tourism product designers to always attach importance to practical research on folk cultural life.

Through the evaluation of a number of bazaars and traditional products that are being exploited, bringing tourists to experience, so these are also well-known destinations such as Can Co bazaar; Bac Ha fair market; sling weaving, brocade embroidery and beeswax painting in Tai Giang Pho; Ban Pho winemaking. However, some markets are lost in terms of cultural identity; the markets are similar, there are no differences; The form of production organization of traditional handicrafts is mainly households, small-scale, and has not yet become a craft village. Households participating in production do not have the skills to serve customers; the products are not diverse, not much use value and artistic value, so the sales power is not high.

2.2. Creating sustainable livelihoods from Periodic markets

To promote tourism associated with the fair, it is necessary to create its own products based on the specific cultural values of each region. Each market should only exploit one strength, one specific product. For example, Bac Ha fair market is a place where the essence and characteristics of the Tay, Nung and Mong ethnic groups are concentrated. The market gathers many traders from ethnic groups near and far to exchange and trade from hoes, shovels to cloth or even buffaloes, horses, pigs, and chickens. Not only that, the Bac Ha fair market also sells precious dog breeds only in the Bac Ha region. Here, people sell dogs from small to large, all very clever with many colors, like species such as shaggy hair, long hair, and curly tail. In addition, the market also sells typical products and remedies of the Northwest. As for the Lai Chau market, it is famous for the products of the mountains and forests such as wild chickens, village pigs, wild honey, wild chickens or traditional handicraft products such as towels, shirts, rattan and bamboo knitting, etc brocade fabric... San Thanh Fair Market (Lai Chau) sells from needles and threads to green vegetables, fruits and even essential products for the family.

Dong Van rock plateau spread over four districts of Meo Vac, Quan Ba, Yen Minh, and Dong Van of Ha Giang province is where nearly 300,000 people live. The people here belong to 17 different ethnic minorities such as Mong, Tay, Dao, Nung, Lo Lo, Pa Than... with their own living customs and products. The market in Ha Giang meets once a week. Ma Le market on Saturday and Meo Vac market on Sunday. People come to the market with very simple goods with a few pounds of rice, a bunch of vegetables, bamboo shoots, chickens, pigs... They also often bring brocade, textiles or home-made agricultural tools such as knives, sickles, plowshares, etc. Especially, the food court here has many specialties such as corn cakes, buckwheat cakes, thang co, men men, au tau porridge... Therefore, the emphasis here is not mountain and forest products, nor handicraft products, but the customs, customs, and traditional dishes of the indigenous people. Exploiting a strength at the market in each region will help tourism here become unique, avoid spreading and being the same.

At the same time, it is necessary to have a planning of the market system associated with the traditional architecture and culture of the region and of the typical ethnic minority communities in the region, which also creates a difference and diversity for cultural tourism products. It is necessary to study and invest in rational organization and presentation in accordance with the traditional style. The issue to be concerned about is that

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the market is not only commercial but also combines cultural and tourism elements, so it is necessary to carefully study to organize traditional cultural activities.

The fixed planning of the market meeting location has been in place so far. This in the long run also makes fair market areas become destinations of historical significance, associated with the history of the region and region. Pay attention to food hygiene and safety at markets. This is also the key point to promote tourism development in association with the exploitation of fair markets in tourism products. Tourism development, especially the development of cultural tourism products of ethnic minorities, requires the direct participation of people, should be supported and trained so that people know how to do tourism and develop the added value of products. This is a correct and practical solution to increase income, create jobs for people in highland areas, and promote sustainable economic development in rural areas, especially in highland areas.

Tourism development must include the link between localities and tour operators in bringing cultural heritage, bringing fair markets into tourism business, bringing tourists to visit and experience. It is necessary to combine with other cultural destinations in the region, forming tours and connecting routes. It is necessary to promote information early and widely, this is an opportunity for tourists to know and come to the highland market.

2.3. Cultural values of Periodic markets and sustainable livelihoods of ethnic minorities

Initially introduced by Robert Chambers, livelihood is defined as a means of income through the use of assets, capabilities, and activities. The sustainability of livelihoods are measured through the level of restoration, preservation, or improvement in assets against pressures and disasters, subsequently ensuring that the next generation has increased opportunities to survive and thrive. (Wu et al., 2023) The theory of sustainable livelihood supposes that people live in unfavorable circumstances and have numerous livelihood capitals. Strategies are developed through distinct methods of utilizing and combining livelihood resources, resulting in different livelihoods outputs. (Natarajan et al., 2022). Based on this theory, several institutions have formed sustainable livelihood frameworks with various focuses. Among those, the framework designed by the UK Department People's sustainable livelihood 433 for International Development (DFID) is widely used (Shahbaz et al., 2007). This framework covers five aspects: (1) Livelihood capital; (2) Background vulnerability; (3) Structure and process transformation; (4) Livelihood output; and (5) Livelihood strategies. The center of this framework is livelihood capital, encompassing natural, physical, financial, social and human capital. (Wu et al., 2023)

Periodic markets assume an integral role in local's lives. (Satyam et al., 2022) Earlier studies have emphasized their important contribution to the rural economy and society as a whole. (Sarkar et al., 2016). These markets create job opportunities and introduce goods and services to rural markets across emerging economies (Aithal, 2012).

Periodic markets greatly contribute to the improvement of economic activities by promoting the growth and development of a region. (McGrath et al., 1993). These rural periodic markets foster the connection of marketing systems to surrounding areas, hence helping form a local trading network throughout emerging economies (Dokmeci et al., 2006).

Periodic markets contribute to the economic development and preserving old cultures. (Pahlevi et al., 2022) The revitalisation of the periodic market is closely associated with proper administration from the government. (Liu et al., 2022). Effective governances aim to satisfy expectations through developing policies and protocols. (Georgios and Barraí, 2021). This action aligns with development efforts, particularly in regional economies based on efficient local administration methods to enhance the welfare of the community (Gerged and Almontaser, 2021). In this context, the rejuvenation of markets stem from the inherent role of the market itself, including economic support, increased incomes and better welfare for local people. (Mursyid et al., 2021). This process relates to the principles of urban spatial planning, contributing to regional development practices to create effective governance (Ye and Liu, 2020)

3. The current situation of some periodic markets in Vietnam

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Ta Sin Thanh periodic market in Dien Bien, Vietnam.

Annually organized in Ta Sin Thang Valley, Tua Chua District, Dien Bien Province, the Ta Sin Thang market is open to the public **on the days of the Rat and Horse** according to the lunar calendar, which occurs **every six days**. The market serves as a cultural exchange and trade hub for the **ethnic minorities of five northern communes** in Tua Chua District (including Sin Chai, Ta Sin Thang, Lao Sa Phung, Trung Thu, and Sinh Phan). **Cars** are recommended vehicles in terms of preferred transportation as the geographical hurdles prove challenging.

Moreover, Ta Sin Thang periodic market has successfully **portrayed and embraced** the **cultural beauty** of the local scene. For, most of the goods sold here are products raised, grown, or caught by local ethnic households. From the aromatic "**Thang Co**" dish to the traditional "**Mong Pê**" liquor and even the **classic costume** which is woven by the hand of the local women, everything provides the most authentic picture of the ethnic culture here - an inspiring and unique experience that no one should ever miss.

Last but not least, Ta Sin Thang serves the purpose of being a **popular tourist destination**. In fact, the market is relatively famous among the community of travel enthusiasts. Whether it is for the picturesque scenery or the beautiful culture, this place truly provides a heaven escape for wanderers who are in much need of peace. All in all, tourism opens up promising opportunities for the local people to generate income while also being able to promote their unique culture to both national and worldwide friends.

(Sources: <https://tripzone.vn/ck10465-cho-phen-ta-sin-thang>)

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(Sources: <https://images.app.goo.gl/48qcsE8Q49bV6TSCA>)

The periodic market of the Hmong people, Vietnam.

Located in Hamlet 10, Cu K'nia Commune, Cu Jút District, Đak Nong Province, the periodic market is held **every Sunday**, attracting a **wide demographic** of participants from nearby communes such as the Edê people, the Mnong people and even the Kinh people. On a weekly basis, the market attracts hundreds of participants with a multitude of **entertaining activities** such as buffalo fighting or renting ethnic costumes. It is the bustling quality of the scene that provides a significant means of income for local households, boosting the **regional economy** as a whole.

It is safe to say that the periodic market contributes greatly to preserving the **diverse cultural landscape** of the 23 brotherly ethnic groups residing in Cu Jút district. No longer a mere space for exchanging goods, the market has manifested itself to be a miniature **close-knit community** where local people could **gather** to share stories of daily life, make friends, and even find a significant other. Especially, it is through the traditional market that many of the traditional dishes such as "Mèn mén" could be preserved and promoted. In other words, the Hmong market has embraced the **ethnic identity** and unique characteristics of the H'Mong people in all entirety.

With the development of tourism in the area, the region is expected to thrive even more. As the place rises in popularity, there are increasingly more opportunities for the locals to make ends meet, providing stable income while effectively promoting Hmong's beautiful culture.

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(Sources: Men men - a specialty of the H'Mong ethnic group introduced at the Highland Market, at the Vietnam Ethnic Culture and Tourism Village (Dong Mo – Son Tay – Hanoi).

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The Hmong people have a diverse and rich spiritual life in terms of customs, religion, beliefs and writing, language, culture and art.

In the community of 54 ethnic groups in Vietnam, the Hmong ethnic group is one of the ethnic groups that is less lost in terms of the traditional cultural identity of the nation. Hmong culture is a component of

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Vietnamese culture, their unique cultural identity has contributed and enriched Vietnamese culture. In the current period of international integration, in order to develop "integration" without dissolving and losing identity, the preservation of national culture requires research, enthusiasm, persistence and long-term research. In this way, cultural values will forever be preserved and promoted.

Lung Phong periodic market in Lao Cai, Vietnam.

Situated in Lung Phong commune, Bac Ha district, Lao Cai province, Lung Phong periodic market is nestled within a long range of majestic mountains. It is the overlapping terrain as well as the vast expanse of the high plateau land that further enhances the bustling atmosphere here. In the middle of the mountains, a lively gem is found.

Furthermore, the local culture could be seen as deeply embedded in products being sold in the market. From the unique medicinal herbs such as lingzhi mushrooms, wild ginseng, or bloodworts to the distinctive "Ban Pho" liquor, each and every item symbolically represents the cultural identity that has been preserved for thousands of years. The fact that doing something as simple as participating in periodic markets could preserve a culture never fails to amaze every one of us.

It is reasonable to state that the Lhung Panh market has successfully served the purpose of being a **popular tourist destination**. Given great potential regarding distinctive culture and friendly people, the place is perfect for traveling enthusiasts. With developing tourism, the market could definitely increase profits which in turn would raise people's income, ensuring better living conditions.

(Sources: <https://thegioitiepthi.danviet.vn/di-cho-lung-phinh-20230816145431574.htm>)

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(Sources: <https://www.bachatourism.com/tour/kham-pha-sac-mau-cho-lung-phinh-va-am-thuc-ban-lien/>)

Dong Van periodic market in Ha Giang, Vietnam:

The fair market is an indispensable traditional culture of the highland people. Dong Van district has many famous markets that leave an impression on tourists from all over the world. In modern life, the fair market of the Stone Plateau still retains its identity, inherent pure essence to create its own characteristics, bearing the sound of mountains and forests and the ancient values of the people of the Stone region.

Dong Van is a traditional periodic market located in Dong Van Plateau, Ha Giang – the northernmost province of Vietnam. Each Sunday, people from different ethnic groups like Hmong, Tay, Bo Y gather here, selling local produce and specialties. Aside from trying local products, participants can engage in special traditional activities like bird fighting or showcase of weaving traditional brocade, which represents traditional values of the local community. For this reason, the market serves as both a cultural exchange and a trading hub for local people.

Cultural values exist in every interesting activity of Dong Van market. From textiles or clothes using traditional embroidery techniques and patterns represent tradition of each ethnic minority group, to local food like mèn mèn (corn cake) or au tau soup, all of them embraces traditional values of local ethnic groups. Special activities like weaving showcases or bird fighting are also an integral part of local culture.

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(Source: mia.vn/cam-nang-du-lich/muon-mau-muon-ve-cho-phien-dong-van-ha-giang-3424)

Dong Van market is also an attractive tourist destination. Nowadays, the market welcomes visitors from surrounding areas, but also from cities afar and overseas countries as well. People come here not only to buy local products but also to enjoy special activities, witnessing the daily life of local ethnic groups. Tourism grants the locals opportunities to generate income to support their lives and promote their cultural values, attracting national and international attention.

Huoi Cuoi periodic market in Son La, northern Vietnam:

Organized every 5 days in the center of Quynh Nhai district, Moc Chau, Son La, Huoi Cuoi is a famous Thai periodic market in Northern Vietnam, attracting numerous local traders and also visitors from afar. Thai people together with ethnic people from surrounding areas will gather from early morning, arranging their products and waiting for potential customers. Products available range from local produce to jewelry or even housewares. With the diverse ethnic community involved in the this market, aside from exchange goods, Huoi Cuoi is also a fascinating place for cultural interaction.

Observing the ranges of products presented at this market, visitors can quickly notice the cultural values of ethnic minorities participating in this market, like Váy côm, towel piêu – those among the best sellers here - are traditional costumes of Thai people. Along with the trading of products between sellers and buyers, visitors can also see the exchange of local customs between ethnic minorities. Together, they share their experiences and form new relationships, thus making the market seem like a festival of diverse culture.

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(Source: asahiluxstay.com/blog/ngam-nhin-cho-phien-moc-chau-da-sac-mau-b589.html)

The unique experience provided in the market is an incentive for tourism. Embracing the scenic beauty of the Moc Chau area and the fascinating diversity of culture, this market attracts visitors from nearby areas and also from cities far away, granting the locals a great opportunity to maintain their lives and promote their cultural beauty to others.

Ha Lau periodic market - notable traditional Dao market in Quang Ninh:

Located in the mountainous commune Ha Lau, Quang Ninh, Ha Lau is a weekly Dao market which blends cultural elements of various ethnic groups. Selling various local products and organizing numerous traditional activities, the market fosters both cultural growth and economic development.

Aside from produce, traditional handicrafts by ethnic minorities are also notable products, which visitors can buy as souvenirs when they return home. Furthermore, the range of activities participants can engage in this market is wide, from traditional games to recreated traditional rituals. Through this, tourists can clearly notice the unique cultural values of ethnic minorities.

With the diversity of products and activities, Ha Lau market is a popular tourist destination. Tourism can boost local income as well as promote cultural values of the area.

4. To be aware of the role of the cultural values of periodic market in creating sustainable livelihoods for ethnic minorities in the northern mountainous areas of Vietnam.

In addition to the beautiful natural scenery, the markets imbued with the identity of ethnic people are a factor that increases the attractiveness of the traveler's journey. This is a resource that needs attention, investment, and value. The highland fair has long been known not only as a place of trade but also a place where the unique cultural features of ethnic groups converge.

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According to Mr. Nhat, "*the fair market in Binh Lieu has many advantages to become a tourism product from its own characteristics, nature has become a tradition of highland markets. It is a vibrant bustle, national cultural colors combined with cultural festivals of the Dao, Tay and San Chi people..*"

The market is also interested in connecting with border tours, visiting the Mooc River, Khe Tien, Milestones... In the future, Dong Van market will be studied and planned into a highland border market, combining border tourism with your country and the provinces of Cao Bang - Lang Son - Ha Giang.

With the fair market of Binh Lieu town, in order to increase its attractiveness, it is expected that the district will organize more night markets, more night art performances, entertainment activities, agricultural trade, specialties, etc. Currently, the market has become a destination, connecting with traditional Ha Long - Binh Lieu tours to scenic spots and villages.

In fact, it can be seen that the characteristics of the fair market have received a lot of attention from localities, but there are still many difficulties. That is the case of some markets in Ba Che and Tien Yen, although they have been interested, but due to the long distance and difficult travel, the access or connection with tourism is not very attractive.

Thus, if you want to form a unique destination or tourism product from the highland market, leaving an impression on tourists, it not only needs the efforts of the locality but also the cooperation of tourism and travel agencies to connect and retain tourists.

In order to promote tourism associated with fairs and craft villages in ethnic minority and mountainous areas, thanks to craft villages, there are more tourism and tourism products that attract many visitors to visit, experience and learn; Thanks to tourism, craft villages develop well thanks to promoting and selling products, needing the attention of authorities and authorities at all levels; have feasible, reasonable and effective solutions. At the same time, it is necessary to have a plan for the market system associated with traditional architecture and culture, in the direction of prioritizing traditional handicraft products and traditional cuisine. Pay attention to food hygiene and safety at markets. Preserve and diversify traditional handmade products.

Tourism development, especially the development of tourism products with the direct participation of the people. continue to provide support and training for people to know how to do tourism and develop the added value of products. This is the right and practical solution to increase income, create jobs for people in highland areas, and promote sustainable economic development in rural areas.

Ms. Thao Thi Tung, Cat Cat village, said that she learned how to weave her mother's fabric from a young age, previously only weaving and embroidering the family's dresses, but now she makes souvenirs to serve tourists. Many tourists, especially children, are very interested in seeing the way of weaving and embroidering cloth of the Mong people. "*I am very happy, both selling goods with money and letting people know about a traditional profession of my people: - Ms. Thao Thi Sung said.*

5. Conclusion

When it comes to fairs, in the downstream as well as in the backth, from ancient times until now, localities have maintained this community activity. However, when it comes to the highlands, it must be affirmed that the fair market is not only a space for exchanging and trading goods but also a form of cultural activity that is unique to the region. In the highlands of the Northwest, it has long been famous for markets such as Bac Ha market (Lao Cai), Mu Cang Chai market (Yen Bai), Muong Lo market (Yen Bai), Can Cau market (Lao Cai), Dong Van market (Ha Giang)... Then there are markets with bold nuances of love such as Khau Vai love market (Ha Giang), Sa Pa love market (Lao Cai). Whenever referring to these sessions and a series of markets in communes and districts of the Northwest highland provinces, people often think of a cultural space with bold highland colors that has been preserved by the people here for generations.

The culture of ethnic minorities in the Northwest highlands is reflected in the culture of going to the market. The fair market in each region is located in the center of the district or commune. The market is not held every day, but the market only takes place on Saturday or Sunday every week. Therefore, after a week of hard work,

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preparing all goods and agricultural products, highland people go to the market every weekend as an indispensable need in their lives. Everyone who goes to the market brings the goods that the family makes to sell at the market. Even some people who do not have goods to bring still come to the market every week. Highland people go to the market as if going to a festival with many expectations to exchange, exchange, buy and sell. Therefore, on weekends in the Northwest highlands, the atmosphere in the crowded and busy market of the highland people has risen to a vitality as if to dispel the cold and desolation in the deep mountains.

At the session market, the identity of costume culture is clearly expressed by people of all ethnic groups. Although life is modern, each ethnic group keeps its own identity in terms of clothing. This is the most obvious presence in traditional culture. When going to the market, people of all ethnic groups wear traditional costumes of their ethnic groups. We can easily feel the idyllic but healthy beauty on the costumes of the Tay people, the brilliant and delicate beauty on the brocade costumes of the Mong people, Dao, Pa Than... It is the costumes worn by the people on them that create typical colors, forming a colorful flower garden in the market. In addition to the costumes worn by the people in the highlands, the costumes sold by the highland people in the stalls have created a traditional beauty in the Northwest market. Those are the products embroidered and woven by the hands of the highland people, sending the concept into it. lifestyle, words eat the voice of their people.

There is a cultural feature that seems invisible and has become a unique feature in the Northwest highland fair, which is the way of selling goods imbued with the concepts of human life of each ethnic group. Over time, the highland people still maintain this unique identity. Prominent in this way of selling goods in the Northwest fair market are the Tay and Mong ethnic groups. Here, there is no bargaining price, bargaining or one less plus two. The seller only sells one price without changing even if the item comes to the market and no one buys it, the fruit and vegetables wither and do not lower the price, even if they have to be brought back, they do not have to sell them all. The reason why in highland markets there is a way to sell at a price at the market comes from the honesty, honesty and frankness of the people. They are people born and raised in the highlands, so they do not know how to challenge, nor do they like to be crooked. At the same time, the steadfastness of the people is also a valuable quality of the highland people in their livelihood in the mountains and streams.

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